

Design and Optimization of Cascade Aerator Using AI-Integrated Software for Bells University of Technology's Water Treatment Plant

Oluwatobi Aiyelokun

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering,
Bells University of Technology, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria

Adewoye Olanipekun ✉

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering,
Bells University of Technology, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria

Daniel Idusuyi

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering,
Bells University of Technology, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria

Opeyemi Bayode

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering,
Bells University of Technology, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria

Quadri Saka

Department of Building Technology,
Bells University of Technology, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT:

This study focuses on the design and optimization of a cascade aerator for Bells University of Technology's water treatment plant to meet future water demand projections. Providing an adequate supply of clean and safe water to the University community is highly critical for the prevention of life threatening waterborne diseases such as cholera, typhoid and dysentery. By utilizing the iNODE Design software, which integrates human-controlled adjustments and artificial intelligence (AI)-driven optimizations, the aerator components such as the inlet shaft, steps and planner area, and collection launder, were meticulously designed. Quantitative parameters, including a calculated inlet shaft diameter of 0.564 meters and flow velocity of 0.2 m/s, adhered to standards from the Central Public Health and Environmental Engineering Organization (CPHEEO) manual. The steps and planner area featured a cascade area of 2.694 m² and four steps, meeting area criteria of 0.018m²/m³/hr. The collection launder, with a flow velocity of 0.6 m/s and total depth of 0.369 meters, ensured effective water collection and transfer. Results obtained showed the aerator design is robust, efficient and capable of handling the anticipated water demands, thereby ensuring a reliable and safe water supply for the university's growing population. This comprehensive approach guarantees the aerator's efficiency in removing dissolved gases and maintaining water quality, laying a foundation for sustainable water supply management amidst campus growth.

Keywords: Water treatment plant, Cascade aerator, iNODE Design software, AI optimization, Clean water.

Suggested Citation: O. Aiyelokun, A. Olanipekun, D. Idusuyi, O. Bayode, Q. Saka, "Design and Optimization of Cascade Aerator Using AI-Integrated Software for Bells University of Technology's Water Treatment Plant," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(5), pp. 118-129, Sep-Oct 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(5\).12](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(5).12)

INTRODUCTION

Easy access to safe, clean and potable water is considered a fundamental human right [1]. However, numerous communities around the world face daunting challenges in ensuring access to clean, safe drinking water, because presently, only a small proportion of the world's total population have access to safe water [2]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) [3], just one billion people out of the six billion people on earth have unrestricted access to water that is safe for drinking. Furthermore, Fadipe *et al.*, [4] reported that this inability to access clean and drinkable water by many people globally continues to persist as millions of children in Southeast Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa have yet to experience consuming clean pipe-borne water. Consequently, this worrying situation denies one sixth of the world's population access to appropriate and modern sanitation facilities [5].

This lack is therefore directly responsible for the growing and worrying increase in water related diseases such as typhoid, cholera and dysentery. There have been at least 6 million reported deaths of children annually caused by water related diseases [6]. As such, the important role that water treatment plants play in the provision of clean water to effectively prevent waterborne diseases cannot be overemphasized. Water treatment plants (WTPs) play a vital role in transforming raw water sources like rivers, lakes, or groundwater into potable water that meets regulatory standards [7]. Designing an efficient and effective WTP requires a multi-stage approach that considers the specific characteristics of the raw water source, desired water quality and local regulations. Traditionally, the design of WTPs has been a time-consuming process reliant on manual data analysis, complex calculations and experience-based optimization [1].

However, this approach is susceptible to delays, inefficiencies, and potential errors. This has motivated the development of more efficient and human controlled artificially intelligent software. According to American Public Health Association (APHA) [8], there are at least seven distinct units in conventional large-scale water treatment plants for urban municipal water supply (screening, aeration, coagulation and flocculation, sedimentation, filtration, chlorination and supplementary treatment). Screening protects the major units and also aids the efficient operation of water treatment plants. If this stage is done properly, Oladejo [9] reported that it will remove suspended and large floating solids present in the influent. These solids could be leaves, twigs, paper, rags and other debris that could obstruct flow through the plant or damage equipment. Aeration according to APHA [8] allows water pass over a series of steps in order to take in oxygen from open air. The aeration chamber is designed to be large enough to accommodate the expected volume of water per time, without overwhelming the unit.

This effectively expels soluble gases such as hydrogen sulphide or carbon dioxide, heavy metals like manganese or iron, and any other gaseous organic compounds that may introduce objectionable taste to the effluent. Coagulation and flocculation removes fine suspended particles (less than 1 μm in size) in water. Coagulants (aluminium sulphate and ferric chloride) carrying a positive electrical charge are added to the water to neutralize the negative electrical charge of the fine suspended particles. This addition causes the fine particles to come together, forming soft, fluffy particles called 'flocs' [10]. According to Adilov *et al.* [11], flocculants (polyelectrolytes) may be later added in a flocculation basin to allow the flocs form larger flocs. Sedimentation allows large flocs that are formed to settle out in a sedimentation tank. The water stays here for several hours, while the sludge accumulated at the base of the tank is subsequently removed for disposal [12].

Filtration separates solids from liquids. Solids that escape the sedimentation tank are expelled by passing the water through beds of gravel and sand. Rapid gravity filters, with a flow rate of 4 – 8 cubic meters per square meter of filter surface per hour are often used [13]. According to Nwankwo and Odenigbo [14], chlorination helps to disinfect the water to remove any remaining pathogenic micro-organisms. Chlorine in the form of gas or liquid (sodium hypochlorite and NaOCl) is the most commonly used disinfectant. Chlorine addition makes the water react with any pollutants present, including micro-organisms, throughout the contact time. The amount of chlorine left after this is called residual chlorine. Ultraviolet radiation is another method of disinfection, but it does not protect water from microbial contamination after leaving the water treatment plant. Supplementary treatment may

be needed in the event that further treatment is required after chlorination. One example of supplementary treatment is the fluoridation of water, where fluoride is added to water as a public health measure to prevent dental decay [4].

However, because of the persistent industrial strikes by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), Academic Staff Union of Polytechnics (ASUP), and Colleges of Education Academic Staff Union (COEASU), Nigeria's public institutions are often shut down, thereby preventing the students of these public tertiary institutions from finishing their programmes according to the ideal academic calendar. Consequently, prospective students of tertiary institutions are increasingly opting for private universities to fulfil their academic objectives because of these recurring industrial strikes [15]. This has therefore led to a significant increase in the number of students enrolling in private universities in Nigeria in recent years, such as Bells University of Technology. Similarly, private university campuses have also had to employ more faculty members and non academic staff as a result of increasing student enrolment.

To this end, private university campuses are facing significant rise in water needs because of increasing numbers of university staff and student enrolment. These needs, directly linked to population and per capita consumption rates, are beyond the capacity of existing water treatment and distribution systems. Therefore, this paper aims to address the challenge of meeting present and future water quantity and quality demands, by designing an aerator as a component of water treatment plant for Bells University of Technology. Maintaining an optimal dissolved oxygen (DO) level is highly essential in various hydrological applications, including water treatment, wastewater treatment, aquaculture, and industrial processes [16]. Since achieving efficient aeration is critical for designing a sustainable WTP in Bells University of Technology, this is why the iNODE Design, which is a human controlled and artificially intelligent software, capable of providing the needed efficiency was used.

The human control aspect empowers designers to adjust design specifications in real-time based on experience and specific needs, while the AI component provides real-time optimization and data-driven decision support. This paper presents the design of an aeration system for Bells University of Technology using iNODE Design software that leverages a human-controlled and artificially intelligent (AI) approach.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of Study Area

Bells University of Technology is located in Ado-Odo Ota Local Government Area, Ogun State, between longitude 3° 9' 41.5908" E and 3° 10' 37.9596" E and latitude 6° 41' 0.2112" N and 46° 41' 27.8988" N as shown in Figure 1. Based on the hydrogeology, the study area lies in the eastern Dahomey Basin. It is underlain by the unconsolidated to semi consolidated Coastal Plain Sand (Benin Formation). Bells University of Technology lies mostly on lowlands, with no evidence of rocky outcrops and series of hills [17]. The primary watercourse responsible for draining the study area is River Atuwara. The water body is a perennial feature that flows through the densely populated Ota town [18].

Water Demand

River Atuwara was selected as the primary source of water for the WTP at Bells University of Technology. This is due to the river's perennial nature, which Ota settlers and the Ogun State Water Corporation currently rely on for water supply. According to the Nigerian Universities Commission [19], the total number of students and staff (teaching and non-teaching) at the Bells University of Technology ranged from 2,554 to 2,829 persons for the years 2017 and 2019, respectively. Assuming a growth rate of 11% per two years, the arithmetic increase method was used to project the population for a 10-year design period (2024–2033). The formula for the arithmetic increase method is presented in equation 1:

$$P_n = P + nI \quad (1)$$

encapsulates the design of three functional sub-units or components, which includes the inlet shaft, steps and planner and collection launders.

Inlet Shaft

The inlet shaft is a structure that links the rising main or gravity main to the aeration foundation. Water from the intake structure reaches the aeration section via this shaft. Since the construction of an aeration fountain must be elevated above ground, this shaft serves as the major load bearing element in addition to providing water to the aerator. The diameter of the inlet shaft was calculated using the equation presented in equation 4:

$$\text{Diameter of Inlet Shaft Required} = \left[\frac{4 \times \text{Designed Flow (m}^3/\text{sec)}}{\pi \times \text{Velocity (m/s)}} \right]^{0.5} \quad (3)$$

The velocity of flow through the inlet shaft was assumed to be 0.2 m/s, the value fell within the recommended range of 0.1 - 0.9 m/sec, based on the Central Public Health and Environmental Engineering Organization (CPHEEO) Manual [22]. The thickness of the inlet shaft was also assumed to be a minimum of 100 mm, while the appropriate values of the velocity and thickness were noted and reported as well.

Steps and Planner

It is very important that water forms a thin layer and breaks down in particles for:

- a) Efficient mixing with oxygen
- b) Removal of CO₂, H₂S and other volatile substances
- c) Reduction of odour and improvement of appearance
- d) Achieving the above criteria demands having enough surface area for water to spread and hence the range is in between 0.015 and 0.045 m²/m³/hr,
- e) Minimum numbers of steps are prescribed so that water can break down into particles. Maximum numbers of steps are defined as over-oxidation may further affect chemical process and also speed up corrosion activity in treatment plant. Minimum rise is prescribed again to ensure good mixture with oxygen in air and maximum to avoid over exposure.

To design the steps and planners of the aerator, some elements were calculated. These included; the area of aerator required, diameter of aerator, size of tread and total height of rise. The mathematical equations used for these computations are presented in equations 5 to 9:

$$\text{Area of Aerator Required} = \text{Designed Flow (m}^3/\text{hr)} \times \text{Criteria (m}^2/\text{m}^3/\text{h)} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Diameter of Aerator} = \sqrt{\frac{4}{\pi} \times A + O \cdot D^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Required Size of Tread (T)} = \frac{\text{Diameter of Aerator} - O \cdot D_{\text{Shaft}}}{2 \times \text{No. of Steps}} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Actual Diameter of Aerator} = (\text{Tread}_{\text{Provided}} \times 2 \times \text{No. of Steps}) + O \cdot D_{\text{Shaft}} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Total Height of Rise} = \text{Rise} \times \text{No. of Steps} \quad (9)$$

The following assumptions were made based on the CPHEEO manual:

Criteria for area of Aerator (recommended range = 0.015 - 0.045 m²/m³/hr), 0.015 m²/m³/hr was assumed

4 number of steps (recommended range = 2 - 6 Nos.) was assumed; and

Rise of each step of 0.2 was assumed (recommended range = 0.2 - 0.4 m).

Collection Launder

The primary function of the collection launder is to collect water from cascades and transfer it to a single channel via Parshall flume. Since the collecting launder is peripheral and water is collected around the channel's diameter, it is assumed that half of the water flows from each side. The channel's velocity should be maintained between 0.6 and 1.25 m/s. The design of the collection launder consisted of two main components, which included the side water depth of collection launder and the total depth of the collection launder. The hydraulic equations used for the calculations are presented in equations 10 and 11:

$$\text{Side Water Depth of Collection Launder} = \frac{\text{Design Flow (m}^3\text{/sec)}}{2 \times \text{Velocity} \times \text{Width of Launder}} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Total Depth of Collection Launder} = SWD_{\text{Launder}} + \text{Free Board} \quad (11)$$

Based on the CPHEEO manual;

Velocity of flow was assumed to be 0.6 m/sec, within the range of 0.6 - 1.25 m/sec

Width of collecting launder was assumed to be 0.6, within the range of 0.6 - 1.8 m, and

A minimum freeboard of 0.3m was assumed.

Figure 2 shows the conceptual design of the aerator.

Figure 2. Conceptual Design of Cascade Aerator (From iNODE Design Academy)

Design Tool

In order to optimize the design process of the WTP, the iNODE Design Software was used as shown in Figure 3 while the design software interface used is shown in Figure 4 as well. iNODE WTP is a SaaS tool for hydraulic design of drinking water treatment plants. The design follows CPHEEO and IS Manuals. This AI-powered tool produces Detail Design Reports, Hydraulic Drawings, and Tender Validation Reports. It has unique Design Management, Design and Drawing, Proof Checking, and Educational Portals. This programme standardizes designs, unifies them, while also saving design

and peer review time. It cuts hydraulic design and drawing preparation time from 15 days (industry average) to 45 minutes. Detailed information on the software can be found at <https://www.inodedesign.com/> [23].

Figure 3. Web Interface of iNODE Design Tool

The image displays the software interface for aerator hydraulic design. The main window is titled "CASCADE AERATOR" and shows a design table for an "Inlet Shaft". The table includes columns for Parameter, Unit, Tendered Criteria, Selected Criteria, and Recommendation. Below the table, there is a "DESIGN CALCULATIONS" section with a table of parameters, formulae used, and calculated values. The interface also shows a sidebar with "ELEMENTS" and various design options like "Parshall Flume", "Flash Mixer Square", etc. At the top right, there are status indicators for "FLOW: 4.31 MLD", "OVERLOADING: 0%", and "LOSS: 0%".

PARAMETER	UNIT	TENDERED CRITERIA	SELECTED CRITERIA	RECOMMENDATION
Number of Inlets	Nos	1	1	
Limiting Velocity	m/sec	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text" value="0.2"/>	✓ 0.1-0.9 m/sec
Internal Diameter	m	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text" value="0.564"/>	✓ 0.564 m
Thickness	m	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text" value="0.2"/>	✓ Minimum 0.100 m
Outer Diameter	m		0.964 m	
Velocity Achieved	m/sec		0.200 m/Sec	✓ 0.1-0.9 m/sec

PARAMETER	FORMULAE USED	CALCULATED VALUES
Designed Flow per Unit	$Designed\ Flow\ per\ Unit = \frac{Flow \times \left[\frac{Overloading}{100} + \frac{Loss}{100} \right] + Flow}{No\ of\ Units}$	4.310 MLD
Designed Flow per Unit	$Q = \frac{Designed\ Flow\ per\ Unit \times 10^3}{24 \times 60 \times 60}$	0.050 m ³ /sec
A _{shaft} required	$A_{Shaft\ Required} = \frac{Q}{V_{Limiting}}$	0.249 m ²
D _{shaft} required	$D_{Shaft\ Required} = \sqrt{\frac{A \times 4}{\pi}}$	0.564 m
D _{shaft} provided	$D_{Shaft\ Provided} = Internal\ Diameter\ (provided) + 2 \times Thickness$	0.964 m

Figure 4. iNODE Design Software Interface for Aerator Hydraulic Design

RESULTS

Projected Population

The projected population for Bells University of Technology from 2023 to 2033 is crucial for determining the water demand and designing the aerator system in the water treatment plant (WTP). Table 1 summarizes the projected population figures based on the arithmetic increase method, assuming an initial population of 2,829 in 2019 and a growth rate of 11% every two years.

Table 1. Project Population for the Project Area

Year	Projected Population
2023	3929
2025	4479
2027	5029
2029	5579
2031	6129
2033	6679

Water Demand

The continuing increase in population directly impacts the water demand for Bells University of Technology. As the population grows, the water treatment plant must be capable of supplying sufficient water to meet both the daily needs and emergency requirements, such as fire demand. The projected population figures were used to calculate the daily and peak water demands, ensuring that the WTP is designed to handle the maximum expected load. The water demand for the aerator for the design year 2033 is detailed in Table 2. The table provides key parameters and calculated values that are critical for designing the WTP to meet the future water needs of Bells University of Technology. Since the aerator must be designed to process the average total water demand (1.596 MLD), it is therefore important for it to also be capable of handling peak demands, represented by MnDD (2.8728 MLD) and MxDD (4.31 MLD). Subsequently, the maximum daily demand was used for the hydraulic calculations of the Aerator.

Table 2. Water Demand for Aerator for 2033 Design Year

Design Parameters	Unit	Value
Design Year	Year	2033
Projected Population	Person	6679
Demand factor	Nil	1.8
Per-capita consumption rate	Litters (Day*Person) ⁻¹	200
Daily water demand (Q)	MLD	1.336
Fire Demand (Q _f)	MLD	0.260
Average Total water demand (Q _t)	MLD	1.596
Minimum daily demand (M _n DD)	MLD	2.8728
Maximum daily demand (M _x DD)	MLD	4.31

Design Estimations of Cascade Aerator

Inlet Shaft

Table 3 outlines the design parameters for the inlet shaft of the cascade aerator, confirming that the provided internal diameter (0.564 m) and flow velocity (0.2 m/s) meets the required ASCE and CPHEEO specifications for handling the designed flow (4.31 MLD). The inlet shaft's dimensions and

flow characteristics were within permissible ranges as well, thereby ensuring efficient and effective operation.

Table 3. Estimated Design Parameters for the Inlet Shaft

Design Parameters	Unit	Value	Validity Check
Number of Units	Nil	1	1) Provided Diameter of 0.564 m = Required Diameter = 0.564 m. OK. 2) Velocity Achieved = 0.200 m/sec. Hence, Velocity achieved is within the permissible Range (0.1-0.9 m/sec). OK
Designed Flow per Unit	MLD	4.31	
Designed Flow per Unit	m ³ /s	0.05	
A _{shaft} required	m ²	0.249	
Thickness of Inlet Shaft	M	0.1	
Velocity of flow through inlet shaft	m/s	0.2	
Internal Diameter of Inlet Shaft Provided	M	0.564	
External Diameter of Inlet Shaft Provided	M	0.764	

Steps and Planner Area

Table 4 shows that the design for the steps and planner area, including the area of the cascade (2.694 m²), diameter of the aerator (2.088 m) and number of steps (4), meets the required criteria for efficient water aeration by ASCE and CPHEEO.

Table 4. Estimated Design Parameters for the Steps and Planner Area

Design Parameters	Unit	Value	Validity Check
Number of Units	Nil	1	1) Actual Area Criteria achieved is within the permissible Limit (0.015-0.045 m ² /m ³ /h). OK
Area of Cascade	m ²	2.694	
Diameter of Aerator	m	2.088	
Actual Area Criteria	m ² /m ³ /hr	0.018	
Number of Steps	Nil	4	
Size of Tread	m	0.155	
Rise Size	m	0.2	
Total Rise Height	m	0.8	

Collection Launder

Table 5 confirms that the collection launder design, with a flow velocity of 0.6 m/s, a total depth of 0.369 m and a free board of 0.3 m, meets the required specifications by ASCE and CPHEEO for efficient water collection and transfer to other parts of a conventional WTP. The detailed schematics of the designed cascade aerator are presented in Figure 5.

Table 5. Estimated Design Parameters for the Collection Launder

Design Parameters	Unit	Value	Validity Check
Velocity of flow	m/s	0.6	Velocity Achieved = 0.6 m/sec. Hence, Velocity achieved is within the permissible Range (0.1-0.9 m/sec). OK
Total Depth of Launder	m	0.369	
Side Water Depth (SWD) of Collection Launder	m	0.069	
Free Board	m	0.3	

Figure 5. Detailed Schematics of the Designed Cascade Aerator

DISCUSSION

The majority of aerator design practices use manual hydraulic calculations, which consumes a lot of time. For instance, the manual method was used by Mechery *et al.*, [24] to design the various components of the water treatment plant units applied to Greater Zab River for the selected location in Erbil City, Iraq. This is also similar to the work of Aziz and Mustafa [25] at Peerlarmozhi and Chalakudy, and Anmol *et al.*, [26] for the design of different but similar water treatment plants. Consequently, the highly innovative iNODE Design software has been developed to reduce the calculation time required to design an entire WTP. To this end, the design of the cascade aerator for Bells University of Technology's water treatment plant has been meticulously tailored to meet the projected water demands for the year 2033, by leveraging on the highly innovative iNODE Design software. The inlet shaft design ensures optimal flow with a provided diameter of 0.564 meters and a velocity of 0.2 m/s, thereby aligning with the recommended ASCE and CPHEEO standards. The steps and planner area, featuring a cascade area of 2.694 m² and four steps, achieve an actual area criterion within the permissible range, ensuring efficient aeration.

Additionally, the collection launder design, with a flow velocity of 0.6 m/s and a total depth of 0.369 meters, confirms effective water collection and channelling. Overall, these findings demonstrate that the aerator design is robust, efficient and capable of handling the anticipated water demands of the university community, by ensuring a reliable and safe water supply for the university's growing population. Using the iNODE Design software which integrates both human control and artificial intelligence was critical in achieving these precise and optimized design outcomes. The human control phase allowed for real-time adjustments and fine-tuning based on experienced insights and specific local requirements, thereby enhancing the adaptability and accuracy of the design process. Concurrently, the AI component facilitated real-time optimization and data-driven decision-making, by significantly reducing the time and potential errors associated with manual calculations. This synergy between human expertise and AI technology not only streamlined the design process, but also ensured that the aerator met all regulatory standards and operational efficiency criteria of [21, 22] design manuals. This initiative therefore presents a forward-thinking approach to modern water treatment plant design.

CONCLUSION

The cascade aerator design for Bells University of Technology's water treatment plant, informed by meticulous calculations and innovative use of iNODE Design software, demonstrates a robust approach to meeting future water demands. By ensuring that the inlet shaft, steps, planner area and collection launder all met the required specifications of the ASCE and the CPHEEO, the design achieves efficient aeration and reliable water delivery. The integration of human expertise with artificial intelligence in the design process enabled precise, real-time adjustments and optimizations, minimizing errors and enhancing efficiency. This comprehensive and adaptive design not only addresses the university's current and projected water needs, it also sets a

precedent for effectively leveraging advanced software tools in water treatment plant design, while equally guaranteeing a sustainable and high-quality water supply for the growing university community. This study recommends the implementation and application of this design in a water treatment plant where the present and future water demands are known or can be calculated, in order to fully maximize its capacity. Further studies can also examine a design that incorporates other units in a water treatment plant such as coagulation/flocculation and disinfection.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest

REFERENCES

1. O. S. Oladejo and A. A. Olanipekun, "Phyto-remediation of municipal run-off using *Typha orientalis* and *Sorghum arundinaceum* in sub-surface constructed wetland system," *International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 211–215, 2018.
2. C. O. Okafor, U. I. Ude, F. N. Okoh, and B. O. Eromonsele, "Safe drinking water: The need and challenges in developing countries," in *Water Quality-New Perspectives*, IntechOpen, 2024, pp. 1-18. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.103479
3. World Health Organization, "Guidelines for drinking-water quality, health criteria and other supporting information," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://iris.who.int>
4. O. O. Fadipe, J. O. Adeosun, K. O. Adeyanju, and M. O. Oguntola, "Characteristics of packaged water under different storage conditions within Osogbo metropolis," *Uniosun Journal of Engineering and Environmental Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 87-97, 2020.
5. C. F. Ezeama and C. C. Achonye, "Analyses of sachet water, bottled water and borehole water consumed in and around Anambra State Polytechnic, Mgbakwu," *Journal of Advance Research in Medical and Health Science*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 21-26, 2023.
6. O. W. Makinde *et al.*, "Assessment of heavy metals bio-availability in stream sediments around a gold mining environment in south-western Nigeria," *Journal of Environmental Application and Science*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 139–147, 2016.
7. Seven Seas Water Group, "Role of municipal water treatment systems," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://sevenseaswater.com/role-of-municipal-water-treatment-systems>
8. American Public Health Association, "Drinking water and public health in the United States," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.apha.org>
9. O. S. Oladejo, *Fundamentals of Environmental Engineering, Handbook of Environmental Engineering*, Olanrewaju Publishers, 2014, pp. 22–34.
10. C. O. Omole and S. A. Isiorho, "Waste management and water quality issues in coastal states of Nigeria: The Ogun State experience," *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 207–217, 2021.
11. T. T. Adilov, M. K. Sarikulov, R. H. Artikbaevich, and N. K. Kuchkarova, "To study the problem of drinking water shortage and public health," *International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 192–196, 2021.
12. United Nations University Institute for Water, Environment and Health, "Global bottled water industry: A review of impacts and trends," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://collections.unu.edu>

13. F. O. Okeola *et al.*, "Investigation on the prolonged storage of packaged water commonly produced in north central, Nigeria," *Journal of the Turkish Chemical Society*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 303-314, 2023. DOI: 10.18596/jotcsa.820949
14. E. J. Nwankwo and C. Odenigbo, "Quality difference between sachet and bottled water produced under the same conditions," *International Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Studies*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 7-12, 2022.
15. P. M. Paul, M. Ogharandukun, S. B. Idakwoji, D. M. Chizoma, and A. D. Odunukwe, "Private universities in Nigeria: Their emergence, proliferation, significance and funding," *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, vol. 12, no. 11, pp. 34-40, 2023.
16. D. Feng *et al.*, "An ensembled method for predicting dissolved oxygen level in aquaculture environment," *Ecological Informatics*, vol. 80, pp. 1-15, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecoinf.2023.101797
17. E. S. Joel *et al.*, "Estimation of aquifer transmissivity from geo-physical data: A case study of Covenant University and environs, Southwestern Nigeria," *Science International*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 3379-3385, 2016.
18. D. O. Omole and E. O. Longe, "Re-aeration coefficient modeling: A case study of River Atuwara in Nigeria," *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 4, no. 10, pp. 1237-1243, 2012.
19. National Universities Commission, "Nigerian universities total students' population," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nuc.edu.ng>
20. Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development, "Structural design manual," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://fmhud.gov.ng>
21. American Society of Civil Engineers, "Codes and standards," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.asce.org>
22. Central Public Health and Environmental Engineering, "Design manual on water supply and treatment systems," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://mohua.gov.in>
23. iNODE Water Treatment Plant, "Hydraulic design software manual for drinking water treatment plants," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.inodedesign.com>
24. A. Mechery *et al.*, "Design of water treatment plant," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 4578-4583, 2019.
25. A. Annmol *et al.*, "Design of water treatment plant," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 4578-4583, 2019.
26. S. Q. Aziz and J. S. Mustafa, "Step-by-step design and calculations for water treatment plant units," *Advances in Environmental Biology*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 1-16, 2019.

